

Supplementary Material for the Paper "Exploring Chemical Reaction Space With Reaction Difference Fingerprints and Parametric t-SNE"

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The Architecture of the Artificial Neural Network

The architecture of our neural network is given in Table 1. It is a fully-connected network with a batch normalization layers and Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation functions.

To train our network we used Adam optimizer with learning rate = 0.002

Table 1: The architecture of the neural network

Layer	Neurons	Batch Normalization
Input	2048	Yes
Hidden 1	2048	Yes
Hidden 2	2048	Yes
Output	2	No

Projections for AtomPair Fingerprints and Topological Torsion Descriptors

We demonstrate the projections of the reactions space obtained with Atom Pair fingerprints (Fig. 1) and Topological Torsion descriptors (Fig. 2). The models were trained for 40 epochs with perplexity 30.

Figure 1: Projection obtained with Atom Pair Fingerprints

Regions on the Reaction Landscape

In Fig. 3-6 a projection for a parametric t-SNE model trained on the Morgan fingerprints with perplexity 30 is explored in more details. We analyzed additional clusters and corresponding reaction types. The global projection is divided into three regions **A**, **B**, **C** (Fig. 3). We prepared separate images for these regions.

Figure 2: Projection obtained with Topological Torsion descriptors

Figure 3: Three regions of interest on the global projection

Figure 4: The region of interest **A**

Figure 5: The region of interest **B**

Figure 6: The region of interest **C**